

Research Article

**Assessing the Prevalence and knowledge of Cardiovascular Risk Factors
among highway construction workers**

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Abstract

The aims of our study were to evaluate the prevalence and knowledge of cardiovascular risk factors in workplace and the global risk among workers. Data collected during these examinations included BMI and blood pressure as well as habits like smoking and physical exercise. The body mass index (BMI) of each worker was calculated and classified into four groups: underweight (BMI < 18.5 kg/m²), normal weight (BMI = 18.5-23.5 kg/m²), overweight (BMI 23.5-26 kg/m²), and obese (BMI > 26 kg/m²). The clinic performed the blood sample test to examine the blood glucose (fasting or random) and the total cholesterol level. Participants with hypertension were 279 (45.07%) whereas 340(54.92%) with no any hypertension. Workers with less than a 10th-grade education were more likely to be in the high-risk category, although this difference was not statistically significant. Fasting blood glucose levels were generally normal in 396 (63.97%) participants. Participants 411 (66.39%) moderate in Physical Activity. Triglyceride was generally Normal in 389 (62.22%). The majority of tobacco and alcohol users were 379 (61.22%) and 286 (46.20%), respectively. in this assessment, 596 know Alcohol consumption raises CVD risk, 503 answers NO to Exercise regularly increases CVD risk, 367 pointed Table salt use increases CVD risk, 569 are aware that obesity increases CVD risk, 602 are aware that smoking increases CVD risk, 538 are aware that hypertension increases CVD risk, and 493 Opted NO to vegetable/fruit eating increases CVD risk.

Keywords: Prevalence, knowledge, Cardiovascular Risk Factors (CVD), highway, construction, workers.

Introduction

The aims of our study were to evaluate the prevalence and knowledge of cardiovascular risk factors in workplace and the global risk among workers at Telangana State, India. Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is a public health problem with a burden of mortality and morbidity that is increasing worldwide. The construction work sector is unarguably one of the most hazardous work environments. This is because the materials and processes involved in the sector expose its workers to health hazards and accidents with significant public health implications.[1] The construction work environment is both complex and dynamic[2]. Major risk factors for CVD are smoking, high blood pressure, high cholesterol, obesity, diabetes, unhealthy diet, sedentary behaviour, and insufficient physical activity. Other risk factors are psychosocial and socio-economic factors like depression or low socio-economic status [11]. There is also evidence that work-related factors contribute to CVD, directly or indirectly by influencing the above-mentioned major risk factors. These work related factors may be physical, chemical, or psychosocial. Shift work, passive smoking, and job strain, among others, are well documented in this respect [12-15]. In South East Asia, an estimated 36% adults have hypertension [3]. In Bangladesh more than 27% of all deaths [4] are thought to be associated with cardiovascular diseases. Epidemiological and experimental studies suggest that high salt consumption is an important risk factor of elevated blood pressure [5,6]. Globally, in 2010, an estimated 1.65 million deaths from cardiovascular diseases were attributed to high salt consumption [7]. Clinical trials and population-based studies have shown that reducing salt intake at the population-level is associated with reduction in rates of hypertension [8,9] and that such strategies are cost effective. However, only a few countries have implemented this successfully as a public health intervention [10].

The closest relationship between blood glucose and total cholesterol was based on the lowest

Chi-square value. The research conducted by Daboul (2011) states that an increase in triglyceride and cholesterol levels is closely related to a rise in blood glucose levels. Therefore, it can be concluded that preventing cardiovascular disease can be done by controlling the increase in blood glucose levels [16]. The underlying mechanism is that unhealthy behavioral risk factors (physical inactivity, unhealthy diets, and smoking) would lead to hypertension, diabetes, high blood cholesterol, and obesity—"intermediate risk factors", which can indicate increased the risk of developing cardiovascular diseases [17]. It is found that modifiable lifestyle behaviors, for example, unhealthy eating, smoking, and lack of physical activity (PA), have been consistently associated with cardiovascular diseases [18-20]. Adopting healthy lifestyle behaviors can be a strategy to reduce the risk of cardiovascular diseases by improving cardiovascular health factors (e.g., blood pressure, blood glucose, blood cholesterol, and weight status). However, most studies on cardiovascular health in construction workers were descriptive studies [21-26]. Construction workers had a high level of occupational PA and were presumably fit, but they were found to have higher risks for poor cardiovascular health than workers in other industries [21,22,24,27], suggesting that PA may not sufficiently protect their cardiovascular health. The associations between healthy behaviors and cardiovascular health factors are worth investigating so that specific health behaviors, other than PA, that may help reduce the risks of cardiovascular diseases could be identified in this specific group.

Materials and Methods

Subjects were chosen from two large construction organizations for a cross-sectional study that was conducted out in January–April, 2023. 619 workers—59 women and 560 men—accepted an invitation to take part in a cross sectional survey. Given the fact that males constitute a large section of the

construction industry, the volunteers who participated in this study are individuals (Male and Female) above the age of 18 years. Table 1 displays the individual characteristics of the survey respondents. Individuals with a diagnosis of cardiovascular disease and those older than 55 were excluded. These workers worked for at least 6-8 hours a day for 7 days a week.

Data collection procedure: This study was carried out in Moinabad (M), Ranga Reddy District, Telangana State, India. The length of the project stretch is 46.533 km. The project stretch passes through shamshabad and Rangareddy Districts and mainly passes through Aziz nagar, Himayat nagar, Moinabad, Appa reddy gudda, Chevella, Indra reddy nagar. This chapter will give a general

description of the project, existing features and design proposals to upgrade the facility to Four/Six-lane divided highway. The study was carried out after obtaining clearance from the Institute Research Committee and Institute Ethics Committee (IEC/128/2023) of Ayaan Institute of Medical Sciences, Kankamidi. Written informed consent was obtained from all study participants after introducing the purpose of the study. Information on study variables was collected using a predesigned pilot tested structured questionnaire.

Statistical Analysis: For the statistical analyses, IBM SPSS Statistics 22 (IBM Corporation, Armonk, NY, USA) was used. P value of 0.05 or less was considered for statistical significant.

Table 1. Socio-demographic details of the study participants (N=619) P= 0.001

Variable	Participants n=619	Percentage%
Age		
18-35	261	42.16
36-45	264	42.64
46-55	94	15.18
Gender		
Male	560	90.46
Female	59	9.53
Working in Years		
1-2	195	31.50
2-4	312	50.40
Above 4	112	18.09
Education		
No formal schooling	269	43.45
1 st – 5 th standard	109	17.60
6 th – 10 th standard	126	20.35
Above 10 th Std	115	18.57
Income In INR		
6000-7000	195	31.50
8000-10000	312	50.40
Above 11000	112	18.09
Marital status		
Unmarried	120	19.38
Married	494	79.80
Others	5	0.80

Data collected during these examinations included BMI and blood pressure as well as habits like smoking and physical exercise. Both automated and aneroid sphygmomanometers were utilized to measure blood pressure. The body mass index (BMI) of each worker was calculated and classified

into four groups: underweight (BMI < 18.5 kg/m²), normal weight (BMI = 18.5-23.5 kg/m²), overweight (BMI 23.5-26 kg/m²), and obese (BMI > 26 kg/m²). The clinic performed the blood sample test to examine the blood glucose (fasting or random) and the total cholesterol level. We were used the automatic integrated LipidoCare (SD Biosensor, REPUBLIC OF KOREA) automatic blood analysis. In this analysis, the results of the workers' fasting blood glucose were measured. In addition, the total cholesterol was measured. The questionnaire included questions on the participants' health behaviors, such as smoking status, alcohol use, physical activity, dietary patterns, and usage of raw table salt. Smoking behaviors were categorized as present, former, or never smoking. The dietary assessment was based on how frequently fruits and vegetables were eaten in a given week.

Table-2: Details of risk factors for CVD among the study participants (N=619).

Cardiovascular Disease risk factors	Participants n=619	Percentage %
Vegetable/fruit consumption		
≥ 5 days/week	240	38.77
< 5 days/week	379	61.22
Raw table salt		
Never	264	42.64
Occasionally	317	51.21
Regularly	38	6.13
BMI		
Underweight	51	8.23
Normal	239	38.61
Overweight	235	37.96
Obese	94	15.18
Hypertension		
Yes	279	45.07
No	340	54.92
Fasting Blood Glucose (FBG), mg/dL		
Normal	396	63.97
Prediabetes	194	31.34
Diabetes	29	4.68
Physical Activity		
Low	138	22.29
Moderate	411	66.39
High	70	11.30
Systolic Blood Pressure (SBP), mmHg		
Normal	245	39.57
Prehypertension	258	41.68
Stage I hypertension	106	17.12
Stage II hypertension	10	1.61
Diastolic Blood Pressure (DBP), mmHg		
Normal	269	43.45
Prehypertension	207	33.44
Stage I hypertension	112	18.09
Stage II hypertension	31	5.008
Triglyceride (TG), mg/dL		
Normal	387	62.52
Borderline	197	31.82

High	35	5.65
Very high	0	0
High Density Lipoprotein cholesterol (HDLc), mg/dL		
Low	208	33.60
Borderline	213	34.41
High	198	31.98
Tobacco/Smoking		
Formerly used	379	61.22
Currently smoking	67	10.82
Never	173	27.94
Alcohol		
Formerly used	286	46.20
Currently taking alcohol	261	34.89
Never	72	11.63

Workers who consume more smoke, salt, and are unaware of hypertension are more likely to have lower literacy levels. In table 2 the observations of the body mass index were Underweight 51 (8.23%), Normal 239 (38.61%), Overweight 235 (37.96%) and obese 94 (15.18%). Consumption of fruits and vegetables in ≥ 5 days per week was 240 (38.77%), and in < 5 days per week, 379 (61.22%). Raw table salt was used -never (264/42.64%), occasionally (317/51.21%), and often (38/6.13%). Participants with hypertension were 279 (45.07%) whereas 340 (54.92%) with no any hypertension. Workers with less than a 10th-grade education were more likely to be in the high-risk category, although this difference was not statistically significant. Fasting blood glucose levels were generally normal in 396 (63.97%) participants. Participants 411 (66.39%) moderate in Physical Activity. Participants having Systolic Blood Pressure Normal in 245 (39.57%), Prehypertension 258 (41.68%), Stage I hypertension 106 (17.12%) and Stage II hypertension 10 (1.61%) whereas Diastolic Blood Pressure Normal in 269 (63.45%), Prehypertension 207 (33.44%), Stage I hypertension 112 (18.09%) and Stage II hypertension 31 (5.0008%). Triglyceride was generally Normal in 389 (62.22%). The majority of tobacco and alcohol users were 379 (61.22%) and 286 (46.20%), respectively.

Table 3-Responses of the CVDs risk factors knowledge questionnaire used in this study (N = 619)

Questions	Options	Response n=619	%	pValue
Use of alcohol intake increases CVDs risk	Yes	596	96.28	0.001
	No	20	3.23	
	Don't Know	3	0.48	
Exercise Regularly increases CVDs risk	Yes	2	0.32	0.002
	No	503	81.26	
	Don't Know	114	18.41	
Use of Table salt increases CVDs risk	Yes	367	59.28	0.001
	No	164	26.49	
	Don't Know	88	14.21	
Obesity increases CVDs risk	Yes	569	91.92	0.014
	No	19	3.06	
	Don't Know	31	5.008	

Smoking increases CVDs risk	Yes	602	97.25	
	No	11	1.77	
	Don't Know	6	0.96	
Hypertension increases CVDs risk	Yes	538	86.91	0.016
	No	0	0	
	Don't Know	81	13.08	
Vegetable/fruit consumption increases CVDs risk	Yes	0	0	0.002
	No	493	79.64	
	Don't Know	126	20.35	

Table 3 shows the responses of participants on the seven questions used to measure their awareness of CVD risk factors; in this assessment, 596 know Alcohol consumption raises CVD risk, 503 answers NO to Exercise regularly increases CVD risk, 367 pointed Table salt use increases CVD risk, 569 are aware that obesity increases CVD risk, 602 are aware that smoking increases CVD risk, 538 are aware that hypertension increases CVD risk, and 493 Opted NO to vegetable/fruit eating increases CVD risk.

Workers without qualifications are often unaware of their stress levels and disease risks. They lack proper expertise in identifying risks, screening for them, and managing stress. Individuals must still prioritize preventative health checks, physical activity, and modifying their health risk factors. Employees at medical institutions should receive regular health checks and have access to nearby exercise facilities.[28]

Discussion

The current study was conducted to investigate the prevalence and understanding of CVD risk factors among highway road construction workers. The CVD risk factors in this study were smoking, alcohol, low exercise, obesity, hypertension, and a lack of vegetables and fruits. Ajayi et al. observed that 31% of adults in Nigeria, South Africa, Tanzania, and Uganda were overweight, which is consistent with our findings i.e. Overweight: 235 (37.96%); obese: 94 (15.18%) [24]. The prevalence of hypertension (45.07%) was detected in this study. The greater prevalence of hypertension in this study might be

attributed to the fact that more than half (57.83%) of the study sample was of middle or older age. Studies have shown that, the consumption of recommended amount of fruits and vegetables reduces the incidence of type 2 diabetes, risk of cancer diseases and prevent weight gain [29–31]. The result also is similar to the study done in South Africa by the South African National Health and Nutrition Survey 2013 which reported low intake of fruits and vegetables among study participants [32]. The World Health Organization reported that, intake of at least five portions of fruits and vegetables per day reduces the risk of non-communicable diseases and ensures sufficiency daily intake of dietary fiber [33]. Therefore, the study to assess cardio protective servings ≥ 5 of fruits and vegetables per day in this study population is recommended so as to understand their portions intake and advice accordingly. The prevalence of diabetes in this study was higher than that of Tanzania national average [34]. However, it is consistent with other studies of urban site in African populations [35, 36]. As a result, more attention should be devoted to the effects of work-related issues on cardiovascular health, as well as the steps that must be done to treat them. Addressing significant cardiovascular risk factors, such as reducing smoking and putting an end to the expanding obesity epidemic, is undoubtedly a problem for workplace health promotion. Priority should be given to sectors and occupations where these risk factors are most prominent or growing fast. Furthermore, health-promoting strategies must be tailored to the particular needs of high-risk occupational groups. The limited

data presented earlier only scratches the surface. A more comprehensive, occupational health-focused approach is needed to truly address the cardiovascular health challenges faced by workers and enhancing health literacy among older and less educated construction workers.

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